

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See *informed consent sheet*

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized transcript of recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	15/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	ALFONSO EGE A DE HARO
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	JUAN JESÚS ECHAIDE
Affiliation of the expert	NAVARRA FEDERATION OF MUNICIPALITIES AND COUNCILS
Position/Job description	COORDINATOR OF THE LOCAL DEVELOPMENT COOPERATION FUND
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	MORE THAN 5 YEARS
Area of expertise	COMMUNICATION
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL AND URBAN

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	<p>In your opinion, are there differences between rural and urban local entities in relation to their interests or main concerns? If so, what are the main differences between rural and urban governments?</p>
	<p>In the context of Navarra, there are three groups of local entities according to the rural-urban classification scheme. The main group, corresponding to 70% of the local entities, consists of municipalities with less than 1,000 inhabitants. A second group is made up of intermediate municipalities (e.g., Tudela). Finally, the capital city of Pamplona belongs to the third group. In the latter case, the differences in terms of interests and objectives (sustainability, economic resources, competences among others) as well as in terms of access to other levels of Administration give the capital city a more independent status with respect to the Federation and the rest of the local entities.</p> <p>The above distribution produces the prevalence of small and rural local entities, which is relevant for the federation itself. In other words, the predominance of small local entities makes the representatives of the municipalities with the largest population aware of the general configuration of the Autonomous Community. Therefore, the rural predominance of local entities is presented as a requirement for any decision to be made at the regional government.</p>
2	<p><i>Do these differences have any consequences on the organization of the association? What mechanisms are in place to ensure equal representation between rural and urban municipalities?</i></p>
	<p>There are no mechanisms for balanced representation, although the dominance of small rural local entities creates in the representatives of other municipalities a general awareness an advocacy in favor of the predominant rural context in the territory of Navarre.</p>
3	<p>Do all the local authorities of the Autonomous Community participate in the association?</p>
	<p>The vast majority of these entities (more than half a thousand) are part of it.</p>

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OPERATION OF THE ASSOCIATION

4	<p>What is the main source of the association's financial resources? What is the importance of the regional and general levels of government in terms of financing?</p> <p>Funds are generated from membership dues and the Local Treasury Fund.</p>
5	<p>Is there a permanent body for the management and representation of local authorities, how are its members elected, are there quotas or guarantees for the representation of less populated local authorities?</p> <p>The Federation has a permanent representative body (Executive Commission) where 2 representatives correspond to the smallest governments (councils). These two representatives are elected by the councils themselves, although the largest representation is achieved by intermediate municipalities in terms of population.</p> <p>The Commission is composed of ex officio members (President and Vice-Presidents of the Federation) and 10 members elected according to the population of the municipalities:</p> <p>Less than 3,000 inhabitants: 4 members From 3,000 to 20,000 inhabitants: 4 members More than 20,000 inhabitants: 2 members</p>
6	<p>What are the main mechanisms used by the association to identify priority issues?</p> <p>The agenda is mainly determined by external actors. In a prominent way and due to the relations (informal and through representative bodies), the regional government is the main actor in the agenda setting. The Federation is constantly consulted on the draft legislation of the Autonomous Community and alerts the regional government on the main issues to be dealt with in order to defend local autonomy. Other relevant actors include the political parties and the Spanish National Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP).</p>
7	<p><i>Are working groups created on specific issues -population, aging, social services, digital agenda-?</i></p>

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	There is a shortage of staff, e.g. the three technical areas (legal, economic and communication) have only one coordinator, who is mainly responsible for the development of plans and projects in other areas (e.g. access to the EU's new generation of funds).
8	What role does party affiliation play in the decision-making processes within the association?
	This is increasingly the case, not so much in the setting of the agenda as in the lining up of the Federation's representatives when the majority vote is the decision rule.
9	Which decision rule is most frequently used within the association: majority vote, unanimity, consensus?
	Consensus but when a vote is cast, the partisan alignments prevail.
10	Are there mechanisms to ensure compliance with the agreements?
	No, there are no control mechanisms, mainly because no agreements are approved that result in specific binding actions.

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

RELATIONS WITH OTHER LEVELS OF GOVERNMENT

11	Which level of government - regional, general government - is the one with which you have the most direct relationship?
	The regional level is the main level, given that it is a single-province Autonomous Community and aspects such as the proximity between the seats of the regional government and the federation play an essential role.
12	What type of relationship is the priority: technical, financial, etc.?
	The main relationship has to do with cooperation in the legislative process, with the submission by the regional government of draft legislation to the Federation or the Federation's initiative to contact the different departments of the regional government to propose plans and programs (for example, in the area of European funds).
13	Is there any permanent coordination body with the Autonomous Administration? If so, what is its purpose? analysis of legislative projects? follow-up of program execution?
	Yes, the Foral Commission of Local Entities, which informs on all the regulations issued by the regional government.

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14	What role does the FEMP play in relation to the association? technical assistance? financial? other?
	The role is limited due to the reduced influence of the Territorial Commission of the FEMP, where the regional associations of municipalities are represented. The FEMP plays an important role in terms of technical assistance and diagnosis on issues such as depopulation. There is not always an alignment of interests, as has been observed recently regarding the management of municipal surpluses to deal with the consequences of the pandemic.
15	Are there relations with other organizations? Universities? Business associations? Trade unions?
	Yes, there are collaboration agreements.
16	How do you guarantee the protection of local autonomy in relation to the acts of other public administrations?
	Mainly through the Foral Committee of Local Entities.
17	What type of relationship exists with the European and international level in general? Is this relationship coordinated directly or through the FEMP, the State General Administration?
	The role of the FEMP, due to its greater capacity in terms of resources, is essential.

Part C: Additional Country-Specific Questions

CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROGRAMS

18	What are the main organizational challenges facing the association?
	The challenges refer to the citizens (impact of e-commerce and teleworking), the local administration (adaptation of the local administration to the predominant rurality in Navarra) and the organization itself (adaptation of a classic structure in legal, economic and communication areas to a modern one with specialization in sectors such as sustainability, digitalization, among others). In relation to the adaptation of the local administration, the main problems are not related to financing but to guaranteeing the service in small municipalities and implementing electronic administration at the local level. Sometimes these issues are dealt with from the perspective of

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	the regional government and external actors (consulting firms) that are not always aligned with the interests of the local level.
19	What are the main public policy challenges - social services, depopulation, etc. - faced by the association?
	Following on from the previous answer, depopulation is an issue that has been on the agenda for some time and is gaining awareness of the magnitude of the problem. The approach to the elaboration of regional plans is top-down and based on plans. These are essential in order to carry out a preliminary diagnostic phase.
20	What measures are being promoted by the association with a view to achieving a population balance and combating depopulation? Are there differences between local authorities with respect to the measures to be adopted in matters such as depopulation?
	The approach is led by the regional government and is based on plans on specific aspects such as employment or subsidies.
21	What measures are being taken by the association in order to be eligible for and participate in the European funds for recovery and resilience?
	A plan of 43 measures to access European funds was proposed to the different departments of the regional government, but the main challenge is that the capacities and competencies of the local authorities do not always coincide with the objectives of the programs designed to obtain (broader) European funds.

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